

EARTHQUAKE INTENSITY ASSESSMENT AND ISOSEISMAL MAP OF THE 2013 MW 7.2 BOHOL EARTHQUAKE

Charmaine V. Villamil, Jeffrey S. Perez and Felomina F. Cayabyab

ABSTRACT: The M_w 7.2 Bohol earthquake on 15 October 2013 was strongly felt in Bohol Island and the rest of Visayas region in central Philippines. It was caused by the movement of the North Bohol Fault, which resulted to surface rupture, coastal uplift, strong ground shaking, liquefaction, earthquake-induced landslide, sinkhole collapse and local tsunami. It brought significant damage to houses and buildings including the collapse of century-old heritage churches. There were around 200 deaths and 600,000 affected families. Estimated cost of damage to public infrastructures like bridges and roads amounted to two billion Philippine pesos. In this study, the intensity per town and city of Bohol province and Metro Cebu is assessed based on earthquake intensity survey, damages from news, and reports of the national disaster management office, local government units, and PHIVOLCS Quick Response Team. Intensities were delineated on the SRTM satellite image to generate the isoseismal map. Maximum intensity is PEIS VIII, felt near the epicentral area and coastlines west to southwest of Bohol Island mostly underlain by soft alluvial sediments and relatively younger limestone. The map may be used to evaluate ground motion characteristics, and correlate the effect of local geology to the observed intensity in a particular site.

KEYWORDS: Bohol earthquake, intensity assessment, isoseismal map, PEIS, North Bohol Fault

1. INTRODUCTION

Based on PHIVOLCS earthquake information no. 3 (2013a), the Bohol earthquake on 15 October 2013 at 8:12 AM had an epicenter at 09.86°N, 124.07°E (Fig. 1) near the boundary of the towns of Sagbayan and Catigbian, and about 34 kilometers N45°E of Tagbilaran City, the island province's capital. The main shock had a moment magnitude (M_w) of 7.2 and focal depth of 12 kilometers. As of 30 November 2013, there were at least 3,900 aftershocks, of which, 110 were reported felt (PHIVOLCS 2013b). The aftershocks recorded by four PHIVOLCS seismic stations were clustered along a NE-SW trending 90-km long band, wherein two-thirds is plotted in the northern and western parts of the island while the rest is offshore towards southeast of Cebu Island (Narag et al. 2014).

The distribution of historical earthquakes in Bohol is dispersed with no distinct pattern (Besana-Ostman et al. 2011). On 08 February 1990, a $M_6.0$ earthquake with maximum intensity of Rossi-Forel VIII was felt in the towns of Jagna, Duero and Guindulman (Umbal et al. 1990). Said intensity was reassessed to PHIVOLCS Earthquake Intensity Scale (PEIS) VIII based on damage reports and accounts of local residents. A tsunami with maximum run-up height of 2.11 meters measured in Anda consequently inundated the coastal towns southeast of the island (Besana-Ostman et al. 2011). In addition, a $M_{5.6}$ earthquake with maximum intensity of PEIS VI hit the towns of Clarin and Inabanga on 27 May 1996 (PHIVOLCS 1996).

Figure 1. Epicenter (star) of the 2013 Mw 7.2 Bohol earthquake and distribution of epicenters of aftershocks (circles)

Generally, the basement rocks in the eastern and northern parts of Bohol Island are Alicia Schist, Ubay Volcanics, Boctol Serpentinite and Talibon Diorite with age ranging from Cretaceous to Paleocene. On top are Oligocene to Pleistocene sedimentary rocks, namely: Ilihan shale where the type section is in Tubigon; Wahig Limestone in the central and northern parts; Carmen Formation in the east and covers 30-40% of the island; Sierra Bullones limestone in the southeast; and youngest limestone in the west - Maribojoc Formation, of which, part of it is the famous Chocolate Hills. Most recent is Quaternary Alluvium, mainly confined in alluvial plains and coastal areas, according to the Mines and Geosciences Bureau (MGB) profile of Region VII.

The Visayan Sea Basin covers large part of Bohol, a portion of Negros and the whole of Cebu (MGB 2004). A basin-like structure bounded by NE-trending limestone ridges on both sides characterizes the central part of Bohol (Umbal et al. 1990). In 2000, PHIVOLCS classified the East Bohol Fault, a NE-trending thrust fault located southeast of the island, as active. Low to moderate shallow earthquakes occurring between Bohol and Cebu Islands indicate the possible existence of offshore faults, although further studies are needed to substantiate this (MGB 2004). Moreover, active faults and trenches in and around neighboring islands of Negros, Cebu and Leyte are potential sources of earthquakes to affect Bohol (Villamil et al. 2016).

The effects of earthquake can be further studied using isoseismal map – lines with equal felt intensity. The map can be an effective tool to evaluate the ground motion characteristics in a certain locality during an earthquake. In spite of its qualitative property, intensity data have vast applications in engineering seismology (Gupta et al. 2013), and in scenario-based hazards assessment and risk reduction planning.

The isoseismal map of the 2013 Bohol earthquake will be generated based on the result of the intensity survey conducted by the authors, documented impacts from online and print news, as well as damage reports from the national disaster management office, local government units (LGUs), and PHIVOLCS Quick Response Team (QRT). Besides, the

effect of local geology to the distribution of earthquake intensity will be considered in the analysis.

2. EFFECTS OF THE 2013 MW 7.2 BOHOL EARTHQUAKE

The North Bohol Fault (NBF), a previously unmapped reverse fault, generated the 2013 M_w 7.2 Bohol earthquake. It is located northwest of the island with a $N40^\circ-60^\circ E$ strike direction and $50^\circ SE$ dip angle (Bacolcol et al. 2014).

2.1 Geologic Hazards

The PHIVOLCS QRT was able to map the surface rupture produced by the movement of the NBF. The mapped rupture in the northern extent was about six kilometers long from Barangay New Anonang, Buenavista (Fig. 2A) to Barangay Napo, Inabanga (Cahulogan et al. 2014). The maximum height of the fault scarp was measured at 2.5 meters (Bacolcol et al. 2014) while the deformation zone in some areas extended up to 50 meters (Cahulogan et al. 2014). The fault movement in the southern extent was manifested by a coastal uplift of 1.5 to 2.5 meters measured in Barangay Punta Cruz, Maribojoc to Barangay Cuasi, Loon. This advanced the shoreline of Barangay Punta Cruz by approximately 50 meters to the sea (Abigania et al. 2014) (Fig. 2B). Plotted aftershocks southwest of Bohol towards Cebu, as shown in Figure 1, may denote offshore extension of the NBF.

The strongest ground shaking at PEIS VIII was reportedly felt in the northern and southwestern towns of Bohol, namely: Antequera, Buenavista, Catigbian, Clarin, Cortes, Loon, Maribojoc, Sagbayan and San Isidro. The islands of Cebu, Negros, Camiguin, Panay, Leyte, Samar, Siquijor, Guimaras, Masbate and Biliran, in addition to some areas in southern Luzon and Mindanao, experienced the earthquake at varying intensities of PEIS I-VII.

Extensive liquefaction was observed near rivers like Napo River, Inabanga (Fig. 2C) and along the shoreline. PHIVOLCS QRT documented lateral spreading, ground fissuring of roads, subsidence of structures like bridges, buoyant rise of buried objects like unconsolidated coralline rocks, and sandboil in open fields (PHIVOLCS 2013b).

Earthquake-induced landslides occurred in areas dominantly underlain by calcareous sediments to coralline limestone, which are chiefly part of the Carmen and Maribojoc Formations. Deep-seated landslides were seen in the mountainous areas of Loon (Fig. 2D) and Maribojoc, while shallow rock falls took place in the famous Chocolate Hills (Daag et al. 2014).

Figures 2A – fault scarp of the North Bohol Fault (NBF) behind a house in Brgy. Anonang, Inabanga; 2B – emerged coastline in Brgy. Punta Cruz, Maribojoc; 2C – extensive lateral spreading along Napo River, Inabanga; and 2D – deep-seated landslide in Loon seen from aerial survey

Various sizes of sinkholes (Fig. 3) were mapped in Tagbilaran City, Antequera, Loon, Maribojoc and Pangangan Island, Calape in Bohol (Manzano et al. 2014). Geologists from the Mines and Geosciences Bureau (MGB) were able to survey limestone-associated structures below using the Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) - a geophysical method that uses high frequency radio waves to image the subsurface (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ground-penetrating_radar).

Figure 3. Collapsed sinkhole that measures around six meters wide

Lastly, Baustista et al. (2014) were able to interview residents of the coastal barangays of Tagbilaran City, Dauis and Panglao in Bohol who reportedly witnessed rise in sea level five to 10 minutes after the earthquake. At least three waves were observed, with heights ranging from 1.5 to 2.5 meters, which destroyed docked boats and inundated houses 10 meters inland.

2.2 Social Impacts

This earthquake brought significant damage to residential houses (Fig. 4A) as well as buildings like town halls (Fig. 4B) in Bohol and the rest of Visayas region. Some affected houses in Bohol were evaluated using the PHIVOLCS 12-point questionnaire “How Safe is my House?” tool. Results showed that 11 out of 22 sample houses scored very low (0-7 points, This is disturbing). Most of the damaged houses were non-engineered, used substandard construction materials (i.e. 4-inch concrete hollow blocks and undersize steel bars), have wide unsupported walls and improper foundation design, and were constructed on sloping grounds (Imai et al. 2015). Numerous century-old heritage churches in Bohol (Fig. 4C) and Cebu collapsed due to the intense ground shaking combined with their unreinforced design. Fissured roads and failed bridges (Fig. 4D) made accessibility of places, and transportation of people and goods difficult (Villamil et al. 2016).

Figures 4A – Damaged two-storey house in Tubigon; 4B – severely-damaged Sagbayan town hall; 4C – collapsed San Pedro Apostol church in Loboc; and 4D – failed Abatan Bridge between the towns of Cortes and Maribojoc (PHIVOLCS QRT and SeRene Project)

Based on the situational report of the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (NDRRMC) as of 03 November 2013, the estimated cost of damage to public infrastructures amounted to at least two billion Philippine pesos (Table 1). Hospital buildings incurred the highest cost of damage (Fig. 5). The Bohol Provincial Engineer’s

Office forwarded to PHIVOLCS the damage assessment report that summarized affected roads with bridge component, hospital and public buildings, and the initial minor rehabilitation activities that the local government had implemented as of May 2014.

The same NDRRMC report accounted for more than 200 deaths and 600,000 affected families. The town of Loon in Bohol held the largest proportion in the number of deaths (31%) and injuries (15%) (Fig. 6), which were mostly due to trauma from falling hard objects and burial from landslide debris.

Table 1. NDRRMC Update: SitRep No. 35 as of 03 November 2013, 6:00 AM

<i>Casualties</i>	
Dead	222
Injured	976
Missing	8
<i>Affected population</i>	
Families	671,103
Persons	3,321,248
<i>Damages</i>	
Houses	
Totally-damaged	14,512
Partially-damaged	58,490
Roads	18
Bridges	41
Cost of damage to infrastructures	Php 2,257,337,182 (~42M US\$)

Figure 5. Breakdown of cost of infrastructure damages (NDRRMC 2013)

Figure 6. Distribution of casualties per town/city in Bohol and Cebu province (NDRRMC 2013)

There was abundance of online news as well as local and national newspaper articles about the impacts up to three months after the main shock. Then trending online videos showed destruction of numerous heritage churches like the collapse of the belfry of Basilica Minore del Sto Nino in Cebu, the oldest Catholic Church in the country. Damages to roads, bridges, town halls and hospital buildings were also written. Other news documented the occurrence of felt aftershocks that could endanger previously affected structures, and trigger secondary hazards like sinkhole collapse and landslides in areas already with tension cracks. The Geologic Disaster Awareness and Preparedness Division (GDAPD) compiled around 427 newspaper clippings, several online articles and videos, and are archived in the PHIVOLCS Main Office in Quezon City.

3. EARTHQUAKE INTENSITY SURVEY

The earthquake intensity survey was conducted to determine the felt intensity in the two research sites: Metro Cebu (four cities and two towns) on 21-24 April 2014, and Bohol province (one city and 47 towns) on 25 April-05 May 2014. The PHIVOLCS survey team was composed of three members per site.

The two-page intensity survey form is in English and contains open-ended questions on:

- respondent's location and activity when the earthquake occurred;
- respondent's reaction during and immediately after the shaking;
- respondent's observations (sight and sound) inside and outside the house/building;
- structural damages (house, building, fence, road, bridge, etc.);
- geologic impacts (ground rupture, liquefaction, landslide, sea level change/tsunami); and
- other notable observations not specified in the questionnaire.

One-on-one semi-structured interview was the survey method employed. Most of the respondents were asked verbally with questions already translated to Tagalog. As they account their experience, several times in Cebuano and Boholano – vernaculars in Visayas, the answers were extracted out. Very few who opted to write the answers themselves were given the blank form and pen. Each interview normally lasted for 10 minutes. There are 732 accomplished survey forms with an average of 13 respondents per town and city.

Results of the field survey supplemented by damage reports from published news, NDRRMC, LGU and PHIVOLCS QRT were assessed using the PEIS to obtain the intensity per town and city in Bohol province and Metro Cebu (Table 2). The PEIS is a 10-point scale used in the Philippines since 1996 with PEIS I being the weakest and X the strongest.

Table 2. Intensity assessment per town and city in Bohol province and Metro Cebu

<i>Province</i>	<i>Town/city</i>	<i>No. of respondents</i>	<i>Assessed intensity</i>
<i>Bohol</i>	<i>Albuquerque</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Alicia</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Anda</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Antequera</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>VIII</i>
	<i>Baclayon</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Balilihan</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>VIII</i>
	<i>Batuan</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Bien Unido</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Bilar</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Buenavista</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>VIII</i>
	<i>C.P. Garcia</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Calape</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>VIII</i>
	<i>Candijay</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Carmen</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>VIII</i>
	<i>Catigbian</i>	<i>18</i>	<i>VIII</i>
	<i>Clarín</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>VIII</i>
	<i>Corella</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Cortes</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>VIII</i>
	<i>Dagohoy</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Danao</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Dauis</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Dimiao</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Duero</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Garcia Hernandez</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>VII</i>
<i>Getafe</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>VII</i>	
<i>Guindulman</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>VII</i>	
<i>Inabanga</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>VIII</i>	
<i>Jagna</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>VII</i>	

	<i>Lila</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Loay</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Loboc</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Loon</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>VIII</i>
	<i>Mabini</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Maribojoc</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>VIII</i>
	<i>Panglao</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Pilar</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Sagbayan</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>VIII</i>
	<i>San Isidro</i>	<i>21</i>	<i>VIII</i>
	<i>San Miguel</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Sevilla</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Sierra Bullones</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Sikatuna</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Tagbilaran City</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Talibon</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Trinidad</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Tubigon</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>VIII</i>
	<i>Ubay</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Valencia</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Argao</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>VII</i>
<i>Cebu</i>	<i>Cebu City</i>	<i>40</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Lapu-Lapu City</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Liloan</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Mandaue City</i>	<i>32</i>	<i>VII</i>
	<i>Talisay City</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>VII</i>
		<i>732</i>	

The effect of local geology to the distribution of earthquake intensity was likewise considered in the analysis. Generally, if the area is underlain by sedimentary rocks like alluvium and limestone that are usually soft and easily crumble, it would have higher intensity. Conversely, those that are underlain by hard volcanics and basement rocks would have relatively lower intensity.

4. ISOSEISMAL MAP OF THE 2013 M_w 7.2 BOHOL EARTHQUAKE

The assessed intensities were plotted and delineated on the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) satellite image to generate the 2013 Bohol earthquake isoseismal map for Bohol province and Metro Cebu (Fig. 7). Based on the map, the maximum intensity of PEIS VIII was felt near the epicentral area and coastlines west to southwest of Bohol Island. Said areas are mostly underlain by Quaternary Alluvium and Pliocene to Pleistocene Maribojoc Limestone (Sajona et al. 1986).

Figure 7. Isoseismal map of the 2013 Mw 7.2 Bohol earthquake. PEIS VIII (dark gray) is delineated near the epicenter (star) and west to southwest of Bohol Island; PEIS VII (light gray) is drawn in the rest of Bohol Island as well as in Metro Cebu

The isoseismal VIII has an elliptical shape with the long axis aligned to the mapped surface rupture of the NBF and its probable southwest extension on land, which was determined based on ground deformation analysis revealed by the Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR) interferogram of the area (Kobayashi 2014). The extension of the NBF further offshore can be interpreted by examining the spatial distribution of the aftershocks. The configuration of this isoseismal shows the narrow and elongated area along the NBF that experienced the highest earthquake intensity, and is affected by the fault rupture propagation (directivity) and site effects (Gupta et al. 2013).

The map also displays PEIS VII in the rest of Bohol Island as well as areas in Metro Cebu covered in this study. Generally, both limestone and volcanics characterized the geology in these areas.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The 2013 M_w 7.2 Bohol earthquake caused by the movement of the NBF triggered geologic hazards: surface rupture, coastal uplift, strong ground shaking, liquefaction, earthquake-induced landslide, sinkhole collapse and local tsunami. Considered one of the destructive earthquakes in central Philippines, it led to the destruction of houses, buildings including century-old heritage churches, roads, bridges and other infrastructures. The cost of infrastructure damages rose up to two billion Philippine pesos or almost 42 million US dollars. Hundreds of people were killed and injured, while millions were internally displaced.

Then available damage reports and field survey data were processed to come up with the intensity assessment per town and city in Bohol province and Metro Cebu. The earthquake intensities in the areas covered in this study are PEIS VIII and VII (equivalent to Modified Mercalli Intensity - MMI VIII and VII, respectively).

As shown in the isoseismal map, PEIS VIII was delineated near the epicentral area and coastlines west to southwest of Bohol Island. The underlying soft alluvial sediments and relatively younger limestone in these areas could have contributed to the very destructive ground shaking felt. The configuration of isoseismal VIII follows both the mapped trace and inferred extension of the NBF. The direction of the NBF's rupture propagation and local geology could have likewise influenced the consequent shape. Meanwhile, PEIS VII was felt in the rest of Bohol Island and Metro Cebu. The lower intensity could be due to the distance of these areas from the earthquake source and the underlying harder crystalline limestone and volcanics.

The isoseismal map may be used to evaluate ground motion characteristics, and to correlate the effect of local geology to the observed intensity in a particular site. An attenuation relation between epicentral distance and intensity may be derived to supplement data for earthquake engineering and geotechnical studies.

Derivative information may be utilized by researchers, scientists and engineers in designing and constructing structures appropriately. It may serve as tool for planners in mainstreaming earthquake hazard assessment and risk management in land use and development plans. Lastly, it may support legislators and local government officials in formulating and enacting disaster risk reduction (DRR) – related policies, ordinances and laws.

REFERENCES

PHIVOLCS (2013a) **Earthquake information no.3**. Available from http://www.phivolcs.dost.gov.ph/html/update_SOEPD/2013_Earthquake_Bulletins/October/2013_1015_0012_B3F.html.

PHIVOLCS (2013b) **The 15 October 2013 Magnitude 7.2 Bohol Earthquake**. Available from http://www.phivolcs.dost.gov.ph/index.php?option=com_phocadownload&view=file&id=73:magnitude-72-bohol-earthquake&Itemid=44.

Narag, I.C., Punongbayan, B.T., Olavere, E.B., Amin, E.Q., Enriquez, M.C., Hernandez, V.C., Soneja, D.S., Melosantos, A.A., Alcones, P., Soriano, K., & Solidum, R.U. (2014) The generator of the Bohol Mw 7.2 earthquake as imaged by earthquakes recorded by the Philippine seismic network. **Asian Seismological Commission (ASC) 10th General Assembly Abstract Volume**, November, 79.

Besana-Ostman, G.M., Ando, M., Daligdig, J.A., Abigania, M.T., Talisic, J.E., Evangelista, N., Listanco, E., & Solidum, R.U. (2011) The 1990 Bohol earthquake: tsunami observation and effects at Bohol Island, Philippines. **Journal of Tsunami Society International**, 30, 78-93.

Umbal, J.V., Masigla, L.M., Medrano, R.N., & Diolata, G.P. (1990) **Report of investigation on the February 8, 1990 earthquake in Bohol province.** Available from http://202.90.128.67/html/update_SOEPD/1990BoholEQ/index-bohol90.html.

PHIVOLCS (1996) **Bohol earthquake - 27 May 1996.** Available from <http://202.90.128.66/1996BoholEQ/index-bohol96.html>.

Mines and Geosciences Bureau Region VII n.d., **Profile – general geology.** Available from <http://mgb-7.orgfree.com/profile.htm>.

Mines and Geosciences Bureau (2004) **Geology and mineral resources of the Philippines (GMRP), Volume I Geology,** Quezon City.

Villamil, C.V., Perez, J.S. & Cayabyab, F.C. (manuscript in preparation) **Impacts and seismic intensity assessment of the 2013 Mw 7.2 Bohol earthquake.**

Gupta, A.K., Chopra, S., Prajapati, S.K., Sutar, A.K., & Bansal, B.K. (2013) Intensity distribution of M4.9 Haryana-Delhi border earthquake. **Natural Hazards**, 68, March, 405-417.

Bacolcol, T.C., Cahulogan, M.T., Punongbayan, B.T., Perez, J.S., Villamil, C.V., Evangelista, N., Hernandez, V.C., Bariso E., Pogay, C.D., Decierdo, P.S., Abigania, M.T., Papiona K.L., Del Monte, L.C., Rivera, D.V., Lim, R.B., Quilalang, M.D., Tabigue, M., & Torre Villas, L. (2014) Geologic impacts of the 15 October 2013 Mw 7.2 North Bohol Fault earthquake, Bohol Island, Philippines. **Asian Seismological Commission (ASC) 10th General Assembly Abstract Volume**, November, 106.

Cahulogan, M.T., Bacolcol, T.C., Papiona K.L., Perez, J.S., Lim, R.B., Pogay, C.D., Buhay, D., Rivera, D.V., Abigania, M.T., Inoue, H., Nakata, T., & Solidum, R.U. (2014) Detailed mapping of the surface fault rupture of North Bohol Fault associated with the 2013 Bohol earthquake. **Asian Seismological Commission (ASC) 10th General Assembly Abstract Volume**, November, 107.

Abigania, M.T., Papiona K.L., Bacolcol, T.C., & Quilalang, M.D. (2014) Co-seismic coastal uplift and subsidence of the 2013 Bohol earthquake. **Asian Seismological Commission (ASC) 10th General Assembly Abstract Volume**, November, 106.

Daag, A.S., Buhay, D., Quilalang, M.D., Pogay, C.D., Lim, R.B., Inoue, H., & Nakata, T. (2014) Landslides triggered by the 2013 magnitude 7.2 Bohol earthquake. **Asian Seismological Commission (ASC) 10th General Assembly Abstract Volume**, November, 84.

Manzano, L.J., Garas, K.L., Ondona, A.C., & Leido, M.V. (2014) Subsidence due to sinkhole collapse triggered by the October 15, 2013 Mw 7.2 earthquake in southwestern Bohol, Philippines. **Asian Seismological Commission (ASC) 10th General Assembly Abstract Volume**, November, 82.

Bautista, M.P., Bautista, B.C., Salcedo, J.C., & Narag, I.C. (2014) Historical tsunamis in the Philippines: 1589-2012. **Asian Seismological Commission (ASC) 10th General Assembly poster presentation**, November.

PHIVOLCS (2014) **How safe is your house?** Available from http://www.phivolcs.dost.gov.ph/index.php?option=com_phocadownload&view=file&id=74:house-safe-is-your-house&Itemid=44.

Imai, H., Nishimura, A., Lanuza, A.G., Penarubia, H.C., Ison, R.S., Tamayo, M.L., Narag, I.C., Solidum, R.U., Inoue, H., Sakuma, J., & Okazaki, K. (2015). Development of Practical Tools for Vulnerability and Safety Evaluation of Houses in the Philippines. *Journal of Disaster Research*, 10, 121-128. Imai, H., Nishimura, A., Lanuza, A.G., Penarubia, H.C., Ison, R.S., Tamayo, M.L., Narag, I.C., Solidum, R.U., Inoue, H., Sakuma, J., & Okazaki, K. (2015) Development of Practical Tools for Vulnerability and Safety Evaluation of Houses in the Philippines. **Journal of Disaster Research**, Vol. 10, 1, February, 1121-128.

NDRRMC Update (2013) **SitRep No. 35 re Effects of Magnitude 7.2 Sagbayan, Bohol Earthquake.** Available from http://www.ndrrmc.gov.ph/attachments/article/1330/Effects_of_Magnitude_7_2_Sagbayan_Bohol_Earthquake_Situational_Report_No_35_as_of_03NOV2013_0600H.pdf.

Sajona, E. G. et al. (1986) **Geology of Bohol.** Available from <http://mgb-7.orgfree.com/profile.htm>.

Kobayashi, Tomokazu (2014) Remarkable ground uplift and reverse fault ruptures for the 2013 Bohol earthquake (Mw 7.1), Philippines, revealed by SAR pixel offset analysis. **Geoscience Letters**, Vol. 1, 1, April, 1.

ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Charmaine V. Villamil is a Science Research Specialist (SRS) and geologist by profession at the Philippine Institute of Volcanology and Seismology (PHIVOLCS) – Department of Science and Technology (DOST). She is currently taking up her MS Environmental Science at the University of the Philippines - Diliman. Email: charmaine.villamil@phivolcs.dost.gov.ph

Jeffrey S. Perez is a Supervising SRS and geologist at PHIVOLCS-DOST. He obtained his MS in Civil and Environmental Engineering in Saitama University, Japan. Email: jeffrey.perez@phivolcs.dost.gov.ph

Felomina C. Cayabyab is also a SRS at PHIVOLCS-DOST. She finished her Master of Community Development at the University of the Philippines - Diliman. Email: felomina.cayabyab@phivolcs.dost.gov.ph

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the PHIVOLCS - Seismological Observation and Earthquake Prediction Division (SOEPD) for the earthquake information and catalogue, PHIVOLCS QRT and MGB mapping team for the field photos, NDRRMC member agencies particularly the Office of Civil Defense (OCD) including their regional offices for the consolidated damage reports, and the Provincial Government of Bohol for the local assistance and cooperation. Gratitude is also extended to PHIVOLCS Director Renato U. Solidum, Jr. and GDAPD Chief Ma. Mylene M. Villegas for the invaluable technical advice. Lastly, to our families and friends for the unspoken yet sincere love and support.